

IMPROVEMENT OF METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN VOCATIONAL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract

This article examines ways to improve foreign language teaching in vocational education institutions using modern innovative approaches and their methodological foundations. Based on a literature review, the advantages of communicative, competency-based, interactive, and CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) approaches are analyzed. The need to develop a foreign language teaching model in vocational education institutions that meets the professional needs of students is also substantiated.

Key words: vocational education, foreign language, teaching methodology, communicative approach, CLIL, interactive education, professional competence.

Introduction

In the context of global integration, foreign language teaching is an important part of the vocational education system, and the need to train specialists capable of meeting the demands of the labor market is growing [1]. Therefore, improving foreign language teaching methods in vocational education organizations is a pressing scientific issue. In our republic, foreign languages are taught at all levels of the continuous education system, from preschool to postgraduate education, in all fields and specialties. While foreign languages are taught to students prior to higher education based on a unified core curriculum, at the higher education level, two areas are distinguished: teaching a foreign language for philological purposes, that is, training future foreign language teachers, and teaching a language for specific purposes and professions in a non-philological field (Language for Specific Purposes, LSP). The purpose of this article is to analyze existing foreign language teaching methods in vocational education organizations and identify ways to improve them based on advanced international experience.

Literature review

The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve the system of teaching foreign languages" (PQ-5117, 2021) created a solid legal basis for the implementation of methodological innovations in this area [2]. Many researchers believe that the methodology of teaching foreign languages should be based on a communicative approach, since it is this approach that develops real communication skills in students [3], [4]. Islamova and Kadirova [5] emphasize the effectiveness of interactive methods in foreign language lessons in vocational educational institutions - such as "debates", "case studies", "role-playing games". A.K. Krupchenko emphasizes that professional linguodidactics arose on the basis of an objective public demand, that is, the need of representatives of various professions to master foreign languages as a means of international exchange of information and experience, and this direction has long been promoted by T. Hutchinson and A. Walters as "English for Specific Purposes" [6]. CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) is also recognized as a modern method—a method of teaching foreign languages using professional disciplines [7], [8]. This approach develops students' language skills in a real professional context.

Research methodology and empirical analysis

To date, more than 300 works on professional linguodidactics have been created in European linguodidactics, examining the basic principles of professional linguodidactics, such as integration, multi-levelness, modelability, variability, communicativeness, modularity, and professional focus. Professional linguodidactics, as a section of linguodidactics, is inextricably linked with didactics, professional pedagogy, professional psychology and psycholinguistics, linguistics, communication theory, and specialized disciplines, which is substantiated by the following provisions [9]:

- when it comes to personal qualities, abilities and professional competence in the formation of professional communicative competence in a foreign language, then a connection with professional psychology and psycholinguistics naturally suggests itself;
- teaching a foreign language is, of course, directly related to professional linguistics and didactics;

- the main goal of teaching foreign languages is to teach professional, industrial and intercultural communication, which means that professional language didactics is also connected with communication theory and ethical standards.

A.K. Krupchenko as the main tasks of professional language didactics [10]:

- clarify the objectives of teaching a foreign language for special purposes;
- determination of the content of professional and industry-specific training in foreign languages
- selection of forms and methods of teaching specialists a foreign language;
- covers issues such as the choice of teaching methods and technical means for professional and vocational teaching of a foreign language.

The core and additional principles of professional linguodidactics are described in detail by A.N. Kuznesov. The main principles include the creation of a socio-professional environment, the requirements of a competency-based approach, integrativeness, consideration of interdisciplinary connections, and a focus on the comprehensive development of professional competencies in a foreign language. Additional principles include the need to consider a number of factors, such as the age of the language learner, learning challenges, modularity, ensuring continuity in language teaching, and the originality and authenticity of materials. Based on these objectives and principles of professional linguodidactics, professional linguodidactics can be interpreted as a science that studies the theoretical foundations of professional and vocational language teaching, as well as its methodological, didactic, and linguistic features.

The content, forms, and means of teaching a foreign language in combination with specialized subjects, which is one of the fundamental principles of professional linguodidactics, were specifically studied by G. Dadamirzaev and K. Fayzullaev, who emphasized the interdisciplinary connections between the fundamentals of academic subjects or the integration of elements from different subjects. In his work, A. Gasanov identified the following types of interdisciplinary connections:

- ✚ methodological and conceptual relevance, contributing to the formation of the worldview of the future specialist;
- ✚ meaningful interdisciplinary connections that ensure the updating of knowledge and skills;

- ✚ educational significance aimed at developing professionally important qualities of the personality of a future specialist;
- ✚ methodological significance, based on the subject and the elements of future professional development.

Methodological approaches and ways of improvement

The following areas are of great importance in improving the process of teaching foreign languages in professional education organizations:

1. Implementing a communicative approach. Lessons should be based on real-life communication situations [3].
2. Professionally oriented language teaching. Terminological vocabulary and exercises based on professional situations develop students' practical speech [5].
3. Using interactive technologies. Project-based work, gamification, and blended learning methods stimulate students' active thinking [4].
4. Digital educational tools. Online platforms (Quizlet, Kahoot, Duolingo for Schools) allow for individualized learning [7].
5. Continuing education for teachers. CLIL and ESP (English for Specific Purposes) training should be organized [8].

Conclusion

Research and literature analysis demonstrate that adapting communicative and interactive approaches to professional needs improves the effectiveness of foreign language teaching in vocational education institutions. The application of cutting-edge pedagogical technologies and innovative approaches in the educational process, as well as the effective use of information technology, particularly artificial intelligence, also contribute to improving the quality of foreign language instruction in vocational education institutions. Therefore, alongside the introduction of methodological innovations, it is essential to develop the innovative competence of teachers.

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